

THE TESTOSTERONE ROLES IN ADOLESCENT MALES FROM HOSPITALS OF HYDERABAD AND JAMSHORO

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Abstract

In all phases of life, **T** (Testosterone) is a key sex hormone required for normal physiological functions. The growth and maintenance of secondary sexual features in men depend on **T**. Additionally, **T** affects bone density, muscle mass, mood, and cognitive ability. Inhuman males experience reproductive problems at various periods of their lives as a result of **T** imbalances. Reduced semen quality in males, a rise in genital abnormalities, and changes in the timing or course of puberty are all associated with low **T** levels. **In this study** on adolescent guys, there was a definite positive correlation between **T** levels, energy levels, and muscle tone was recorded. The amount of **T** in **AD** (Adolescent) males increases 20 to 30 fold, boosting secondary sexual characteristics, **MM** (Muscle Mass), **BD** (Bone Density), and the **(B)** behavior. **T** influences anabolic and androgenic effects in **AD** by promoting protein synthesis, which leads to tissue development and the proliferation of **AR** (Androgen Receptor). Partakers (**Sample**) were **120 AD** males having age above 13 and below 20. As (**AD** according to **WHO** (World Health Organization) range 11 to 19). The study was conducted during the January 2021 to July 2022, from highly populated cities Hyderabad and Jamshoro.

Keywords: Testosterone; Adolescent Males; Hormone; Hyderabad; Jamshoro.

INTRODUCTION

(T)Testosterone: A key steroid hormone in male (humans), **T** regulates sex differentiation and has a vital role in adolescent male traits, spermatogenesis and fertility [1-3]. In men, the testes create the majority of testosterone (95%), with the adrenal gland producing the remaining 5%. Teenage boy's **MH** (Mental health) and **B** (behavior) are caused by a 20–30 fold increase in testosterone during adolescence. Testosterone influences the anabolic and androgenic actions in **AD** (Adolescent male), as well as the proliferation of tissues and androgen receptors **AR**. Its effects on the adolescent age, **T** increases the **anabolic effects AE** like increased bone density, increased bone strength, muscle mass, muscle strength, linear growth and bone development. While its **androgenic effects AF** during the adolescent stage are Sexual organ maturation, Fontal scrotum development, Voice deepening and Facial and axillary hair growth [4-5]. **LTL Low testosterone levels** in adolescent males are connected with androgenic and anabolic effects that lead to loss of muscular mass and strength (sarcopenia), as well as chronic sickness or ageing. Based on the fact that **T** raise **MM** and **MH** and enhance

measures of muscle performance, particularly in skeletal muscles **SM**, and that changes in **SM** performance brought on by testosterone translate into benefits in athletic performance **AP** and outcomes related to health. The rationale behind the increase in **MM** and maximal MS with **T** treatment in many clinical and experimental scenarios remains unproven. However, it is unknown whether **T** may be used to good effect without causing major, long-lasting bad effects or whether it can help **AP** and health-related issues [6].

On the other hand a high **T** level in men, **have no problem**. You might be surprised if someone shows you at a little league game what you initially interpret as inappropriate sexual behavior, street violence, or arguments between fathers. Part of that may be due to the challenge of determining appropriate testosterone levels and normal behavior. Blood **T** levels can fluctuate dramatically throughout the day and over time. Very high **T** cause sperm count problems, testicular atrophy and impotence, heart muscle damage, and increased risk of heart attack [7-8].

In AD, **T** is the most vital hormone that affects on the development of physical and behavioral masculinity. It has been linked for years to the arousal of sexual behavior as well as the induction of aggressive and dominance behavior in people. The main sex hormone, **T** controls spermatogenesis and fertility. **T** levels grow 20 to 30 times during adolescence. The information currently available on the relationship between **T** and aggression, as well as **AD** male aggression-related traits or attitudes, is consistent with the general theory that behavior and gonadal **T** production interact in a regulating loop with behavior acting as either a cause or an effect [9-10]. The behavior-to-hormones causal influences in **AD** males are currently far better understood than the opposite. **T** fluctuations after nonaggressive social challenges are the finest example of this, with good and negative outcomes causing, respectively, short-term increases and decreases in the hormone level. **T** and aggression-related behavioral traits are positively correlated in teenage males. Pre- and early **AD**, on the other hand, offer less conclusive evidence of **T** aggressive connection [12-15]. **AD** is characterized by significant physical, psychological, and social development while it is linked to a variety of emotional and behavioral issues, including increased rates of depression, suicidality, and substance addiction [16]. **AD** is a period of puberty and the age of legal maturity [17-20]. The teenagers means adolescence, the word youth means maturity and while **AD** is the period between the ages of 10 and 19, which is very important in laying the foundations for future health. **AD** go through a rapid period of physical cognitive and psychosocial development [21-28].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Data Collection: was made from Government and Private Institutions and some local clinics of Hyderabad and Jamshoro (**Fig. 1**) from **January 2021 to July 2022**. **Sampling:** for the study were made according to standard methods, like comparative analysis of the various roles of T an T levels, BMI, Diurnal rhythms and Nutrition were carried out by two

methods one by chemical analysis of the blood sample and by questionnaires. The sample size was 120 AD males having age above 13 and below 20 (**Fig. 2 to 5**). No partakers took any drug, inhalant or other drugs that produce artificial pleasure. All partakers were volunteers. Foremost all the Adolescent males were demonstrated the importance of T. On their request they were given guarantee while their name will not be mentioned in the thesis. Partakers blood sample were taken once in two months, in order to observe role of T during AD with related to their BMI, Diurnal rhythms and nutrition. 3ml Blood of AD male was tested through serum human ELISA test in Diagnostic lab of LUMHS. All samples were stored at 20°C until assays were performed.

Figure 1: Map of Hyderabad, Jamshoro, Sindh Pakistan from where Data was Collected

Figure 2: Showing AD Males of 14 to 16 Age Group

Figure 3: Showing AD Males of 17 to 19 Age Group

Figure 4: Showing AD Males of 14 to 16 Age Group

Figure 5: Showing AD Males of 14 to 16 Age Group

RESULTS

The present study was carried out on the **T** role during **AD** period (14 to 19 age). This age group has peak levels of **T** secretion and dynamic changes. It was found that the level of **T** is affected with some factors which include **BMI**, Nutrition and diurnal rhythms. For this study, **120** AD male were studied which were divided into two age groups. Group-I of AD from **14** to **16** years of age called initial **AD** period (IADP), Group-II of AD from 17 to **19** years of age called peak AD period (PADP). During IADP levels of **T** normally range from 20ng/dl to 1000ng/dl (**Table. 1**). Level below 300ng/dl needs serious attention regarding **T**. During PADP levels of **T** normally range from 300ng/dl to 1200ng/dl. The Level of **T** related to age in AD with BMI explained and compared in the (**Table.2**). All those AD male having well **T** level are those who follows diurnal rhythms and taking essential nutrients for the development of **T**. During AD level of **T** increases with age mean intensity of **T** increases.

Table 1: Normal Range of Testosterone

Age/ Group	Normal Range of Testosterone Level
14-to-16 Group-I (IADP)	20 to 800 nanograms per deciliter (ng/dl)
17-to-19 Group-II (PADP)	300 to 1000 nanograms per deciliter (ng/dl)

Table 2: Comparison of Testosterone with BMI

Age	Testosterone level Mean ± Sd	BMI Mean ± Sd
14(IADP)	253.65 ± 121.10	19.185 ± 2.529
15 (IADP)	314.4 ± 137.35	19.26 ± 2.238
16 (IADP)	345.6 ± 76.75	21.025 ± 2.295
17(PADP)	324.25 ± 87.24	19.65 ± 1.67
18 (PADP)	352 ± 112.15	21.77 ± 2.536
19 (PADP)	360.3 ± 96.59	21.75 ± 3.73

LEVEL OF T IN DURING IADP (14)

In the initial adolescent period **IADP** (age of 14 years) level of **T** range from 20 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics not near to half of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl or 200ng/dl, were those AD which had disturbed diurnal rhythms, disturb BMI and most of them skip breakfast potentially needed for major nutrition in AD male and nutrition enhances **T** level in AD.

Figure 6: Level of T during IADP (14)

LEVEL OF T IN DURING IADP (15)

In IADP (age of 15 years) level of testosterone range from 20 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics not near to half of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl or 200ng/dl. While same results were found as in 14 age group.

Figure 7: Level of T during IADP (15)

LEVEL OF T IN DURING IADP (16)

In IADP (age of 16 years) level of testosterone range from 20 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics not near to half of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl no one below 200ng/dl, those who were below 300 ng/dl AD males. Remaining same results were found as in 14, 15 age groups.

Figure 8: Level of T during IADP (16)

LEVEL OF T IN DURING PADP (17)

In PADP (age of 17 years) level of T range from 300 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics not near to half of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl no one below 200ng/dl, those who were below 300 ng/dl AD males. While same results were found as in 14, 15, 16 age groups.

Figure 9: Level of T during PADP (17)

LEVEL OF T IN DURING PADP (18)

In PADP (age of 18 years) level of testosterone range from 300 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics some were near to middle of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl or 200ng/dl, those who were below 300 ng/dl or 200 ng/dl AD males. Remaining same results were found as in 14, 15, 16, 17 age groups.

Figure 10: Level of T during PADP (18)

LEVEL OF T IN DURING PADP (19)

In PADP (age of 19 years) level of testosterone range from 300 ng /dl to 1200 ng /dl but below statistics some were near to middle of peak level, while most of these above lowest level, they were in between the middle range some were below to 300ng/dl or 200ng/dl, those who were below 300 ng/dl or 200 ng/dl AD males. Remaining same results were found as in 14, 15,16,17,18 age groups.

Figure 11: Level of T during PADP (19)

COMPARISON OF T LEVEL IN IADP

This spectrum of T hormone among IADP show clear cut evidence that with age, T level increases in AD, all AD males were near to middle range of normal T level. Some were found below to middle points and a few were below to cut points (300ng/dl) (Fig.12). Those AD who were below to cut points of T level were with low and high BMI as compared to healthy BMI. Some other factors which found to influences on T level include diurnal rhythms and nutrition. AD male had healthy T level were those follows diurnal rhythms and takes 6 to 8 hours sleep in night. A major factor for normal T level in AD is nutrition those who were taking healthy breakfast had better T level as compare to those who skipped breakfast. Not only breakfast while had sea food or fish once in week to fulfill the nutritional requirement as salmon, prawn and some other fishes provides essential minerals and vitamins for the production of T in AD males. Mean T level during IADP is 304.55 ng/d.

Figure 12: Comparison of T level in IADP (14 to 16)

COMPARISON OF T LEVEL IN PADP

This spectrum of T among PADP, show that along with age, T hormone level increases in AD, and measured near to middle range of normal. Some were below to middle points and even some were below to cut points (300ng/dl) (Fig.13). While other results all almost and recommendations are same as in the IADP. Mean T level during PADP is 345.51 ng /dl.

T levels during IADP and PADP show a strong evident that it increases with age.

Figure 13: Comparison of T level in PADP (17 to 19)

Figure 14: Comparison of T levels during IADP AND PADP

BMI DURING AD

In **AD**; **BMI** is found healthy which ranges from 16 kg/ m² to 26.2 kg/m², **AD** with below 16 kg/ m² considered as underweight and **AD** with 26.3 kg/ m² to 29.3 considered as overweight and **AD** with 29.4 kg/ m² considered as obese (**Table.3**). And research findings clearly indicate that how T levels maintained with diurnal, from above results indicate that diurnal rhythms or circadian cycle had strong impact on T levels, variations in T levels associated with changes in diurnal rhythms as shown in (**Fig.15**).

Table 3: BMI of the AD

Age	Healthy BMI	Underweight	Overweight	Obese
14	16kg/ m ² to 23.5 kg/ m ²	15.9 kg/ m ² or below	23.6 kg/ m ² to 25.9 kg/ m ²	26 kg/ m ² or above
15	16.7 kg/ m ² to 23.3 kg/ m ²	16.6 kg/ m ² or below	23.4kg/ m ² to 26.7 kg/ m ²	26.8 kg/ m ² or above
16	17.3 kg/ m ² to 24.1 kg/ m ²	17.2 kg/ m ² or below	24.2kg/ m ² to 27.4 kg/ m ²	27.5 kg/ m ² or above
17	17.7kg/ m ² to 24.8 kg/ m ²	17.6 kg/ m ² or below	24.9kg/ m ² to 28.1 kg/ m ²	28.2 kg/ m ² or above

18	18.2kg/ m ² to 25.5 kg/ m ²	18.1 kg/ m ² or below	25.6kg/ m ² to 28.8 kg/ m ²	28.9 kg/ m ² or above
19	18.7kg/ m ² to 26.2 kg/ m ²	18.6 kg/ m ² or below	26.3kg/ m ² to 29.8 kg/ m ²	29.9 kg/ m ² or above

Figure 15: Diurnal Rhythms with Variation T levels

DISCUSSION

T (testosterone) is vital hormone for the development of secondary sex characters in **AD** period. All these physical, behavioral, anabolic and androgenic activities are carried out by primary sex hormone is **T**. **AD** is period of dynamic changes in physical and behavioral structure in males. During AD level of T increases about 20 to 30 folds. It was found that T level linked with behavioral problems during AD as reported by [12]. It was found that the level of T is related to BMI, Diurnal rhythms and nutrition. High T level doesn't mean development of early AD but it is related to excess, road rage, fighting at little league games and sexual iniquity. I have found that AD with little high T were more aggressive and develop acne on skin. In most of AD having better level of T level were those taking fatty fish or meat in diet once a week as review shows [16] fatty fish like sardines and salmon necessary for hormonal health during AD. I have found that food with micronutrients like Zn and Mg good source of T health among AD. In review shows that nutrient rich with Zn and Mg great source to enhance T during AD [26]. However we had found during research AD males with minute change in T levels leads to behavioral issues as discussed by booth et al. research suggest that strong connection between diurnal rhythms associated with T levels in AD, minor differences in T levels linked with diurnal rhythms suggested by [10]. The Diurnal Rhythms of T levels is more influenced in AD males that shows larger correlations with age and pubertal status as compared to females suggest by [12]. High and low BMI influence on normal morphology of T levels in AD [20]. About 30 AD out of 120 total AD with variation in BMI having changes in levels of T as compare to their age group. We found 73% AD males with T levels near to middle range of normal which show diurnal rhythms, while 27% AD males with change in T levels were

those AD males with variation in diurnal rhythms as showed in [25]. T levels in AD males decrease each hour across the day, AD sample taken in early morning between 8 am to 10 am having better curve as compare to those AD males who given samples in evening 8 pm to 10pm as in previous studies levels of T in AD during day time was carried out by [26]. I find that AD males with low attentions, anxiety and depression issues were those with little bit change in T levels as compare to normal range in T levels as discussed by Booth and colleagues during 1999 that depression in AD is associated with low T levels. AD males with better or good T levels were less normal having depression, anxiety and attention issues as compare to those AD with little change in T levels. It was fond during this research that T levels influences not only sexual characters, anabolic and androgenic activities in AD but it also influences AD behavior, concentration (attention). Higher level of depression, anxiety linked with variation or low levels of T during day time or it is linked with diurnal rhythms. During AD protein metabolism is associated with muscle strength and mass linked with nutrients necessary for activating T in AD. I found that AD males taking protein rich nutrients once in week or twice a week having normal range of T levels as compare to those who had no proper diet to maintain T levels . However many researchers suggest that changes in T levels without the use of anabolic steroids has been a highly investigated area because T levels enhancing AP [6, 15].

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